

A simple cost effective method for obtaining intact shell cenospheres from as received one

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Abstract : One of the most important value added material found in fly ash are cenospheres. The as received cenospheres collected from an ash lagoon of a super thermal power plant with its size classified fractions were thoroughly characterised. It was revealed that the physical and morphological property differs. Using Scanning Electron Microscopy (SEM) it was found that among the sieved fractions, the coarsest fraction (containing 90–96% by weight of the total as received cenosphere) contains the major fraction of intact shell cenospheres whereas the finest fraction contains mainly the broken one. Further flotation of the coarsest fraction in acetone leads to isolation of a density separated fraction which is lighter and has a higher content of intact shell cenospheres. This floated fraction may act as a better potent for industrial application.

Keywords : Fly ash, cenospheres, beneficiation, SEM, float, intact shell.

Introduction

Cenospheres, the hollow ceramic microspheres found in fly ash derive its name from the Greek words *kenos* (hollow) and *sphaira* (sphere)¹. These are light, hollow particles mostly thin walled (wall thickness ~4 μm) – the shell thickness being 5–10% of the particle diameter^{2–4}. The particle size of cenospheres varies from 5–500 μm . Literature reports suggest that the most common particle size range is 20–250 μm ^{2,5}. Cenospheres are formed during the combustion of coal in thermal power plants through an intricate mechanism and has been the subject of some invasive investigations^{2,6}. The first report dates back to 1966, which relates cenosphere formation due to melting of intrinsic mineral matters on a non-wetting surface, namely carbon⁷. It was proposed that the gases generated inside the molten droplet inflate it resulting in the formation of cenospheres. Various stages of gas generation were outlined. However, some of the mechanisms proposed were rather qualitative and there

was a need to explain the formation of cenospheres on the basis of some established principles of chemistry rather than the process of formation as a complex physico-chemical phenomenon⁴.

The chemical composition of cenospheres is quite akin to that of fly ash particles, though there are reports that Si, Al, Na, K, Ti, Fe content are higher as compared to the as received fly ash composition^{2,8,9}. Density of cenospheres is $< 1 \text{ g cm}^{-3}$, thus facilitating their extraction from fly ash simply by dispersion in water. The bulk and apparent densities of fly ash lies in the range of 0.2–0.5 and 0.4–0.8 g cm^{-1} respectively^{2,8}. Phase mineralogical analysis of cenospheres using X-ray diffraction (XRD) reveals that predominant mineralogical phases present are quartz, mullite, magnetite, hematite, calcite etc.¹⁰. Thermal analysis of ceramic cenospheres has revealed that these decrepitate at around 300 °C with loss of water and sinter around 1200 °C^{3,11}. Cenospheres have good mechanical properties as well (average compressive strength of 3000+ psi)¹².

Some of the unique properties of cenospheres such as good thermal insulation, ability to absorb sound, light weight, spherical shape, inertness to acid, high thermal stability, shielding of electromagnetic interference etc. make it a very useful candidate for various industrial applications¹⁰. Cenospheres have been used as lightweight fillers in polymers and paints^{8,13,14}. Lightweight concrete has also been manufactured using cenospheres¹⁵. Other applications are in the field of ceramics, plastics, construction, recreation, automotive energy and technology¹⁰. Utilization of cenosphere is not only essential from environmental point of view but also when incorporated in finished products improves its property in a cost effective manner. However, for such applications, it is not only essential to characterise the as received cenospheres (from ash lagoon), but also to devise methodologies so that beneficiated fractions enriched in 'intact shell' cenospheres are obtained. Of particular disadvantage regarding specific applications is the presence of broken cenospheres, which partially affects the unique properties of the finished products when incorporated. Thus, the thermal and sound insulating properties are greatly affected when the percent abundance of 'intact shell' cenospheres is low in a sample of as received cenospheres. It is therefore necessary to carry out proper processing of the "as received cenospheres" for specific end uses.

Cenospheres that are generated in most of the Indian thermal power plants contain a substantial amount of broken one. Hence, a proper processing of the cenospheres (as received) is necessary to make these specific application oriented. The present communication reflects the focused effort in this direction. Apriori, methodologies were devised to characterise the as received cenospheres from ash lagoon of Rihand Super Thermal Power Plant, Sonbhadra, Uttar Pradesh, India. The physico-chemical characteristics of cenospheres, inclusive of the morphological features were determined. Based on the results of characterisation, methodologies were devised for beneficiation of the as received cenospheres.

Materials and methods :

Cenosphere samples were collected from ash lagoon of Rihand Super Thermal Power Plant, Sonbhadra, Uttar

Pradesh, India. For obtaining a representative sample the cenosphere samples were collected directly from ash lagoon (2 kg day⁻¹) over a period of one month. The cenospheres thus collected, were washed with water several times to remove adhering impurities. Subsequently, the floating cenospheres were collected. The adhering water droplets were wiped out using filter paper. Thereafter, the cenosphere sample was subjected to 'coning and quartering' – a standard method for obtaining homogeneous representative sample. From 60 kg of cenospheres collected from ash lagoon (as mentioned earlier), 10 kg of representative cenosphere samples was prepared. Finally, the prepared sample was washed with acetone and dried at 70 °C for 2 h to obtain a dried representative sample. The representative sample thus prepared was thoroughly characterised in respect of their various properties like bulk density, apparent density, particle size (Fritsch particle size analyzer, Analysette-Fritsch, Germany). Scanning Electron Microscopy (Model S-440, LEO Electron Microscopy, LEO, Oxford, UK) and High Resolution Transmission Electron Microscopy (High resolution TEM, JEOL-JEM 2100, JEOL Ltd., Tokyo, Japan) were used for morphological analysis. Phase mineralogical analysis was carried out using X-ray Diffraction (CuK_α radiation, scan angle, 2θ = 10–90°, Model-XD-D1 diffractometer, 40 kV, 40 mA, Shimadzu Corporation, Japan). Chemical composition of cenosphere sample was determined using X-ray fluorescence (Phillips AXIOS, Pan Analytical, Phillips, Almelo, Netherlands). For measurement of bulk and apparent densities at least twenty samples were used for each fraction so that a close to true picture is obtained. Similarly, for morphological analysis using SEM, ten randomly chosen samples were used for each of the as received, size classified fractions, floated and settled cenospheres.

The methodology followed for beneficiation is outlined in Scheme 1. Physical separation by mechanical sieving followed by density separation (using acetone) of a size classified cenosphere fraction which has been obtained by the first step results in a size and density classified fraction which is not only rich in intact shell cenospheres but also lighter (lower density, $\rho_{\text{apparent}} = 618 \text{ kg m}^{-3}$).

Dey *et al.* : A simple cost effective method for obtaining intact shell cenospheres from as received one

Scheme 1. Flow sheet for size classification/beneficiation of as received cenospheres.

A : cenospheres retained by sieve no. 150 ($> 104 \mu\text{m}$). B : cenospheres passed through sieve no. 150 but retained by sieve no. 250 ($< 104 \mu\text{m}$ to $> 66 \mu\text{m}$). C : cenospheres passed through sieve no. 250 but retained by sieve no. 300 ($< 66 \mu\text{m}$ to $> 53 \mu\text{m}$). D : cenospheres passed through sieve no. 300 but retained by sieve no. 400 ($< 53 \mu\text{m}$ to $> 38 \mu\text{m}$). E : cenospheres passed through sieve no. 400 ($< 38 \mu\text{m}$). B.S. : based on pore size of sieves, British Standard.

Dried representative samples of cenospheres were size classified by sieving with sieves of mesh size 150, 250, 300 and 400 using a sieve shaker for duration of about 20 min. Each fraction was collected and subsequently weighed. Such size classification is necessary to identify fraction/s which will have maximum percentage of intact shell cenospheres. Each of the size classified fractions thus obtained was characterised. Bulk and apparent density of such size classified fractions were determined. Morphological analysis for such fractions was carried out using SEM. Flotation of cenospheres belonging to fraction A of size classified cenospheres was carried out in two phases – first by dispersing the cenospheres in water (cenosphere : water ratio 50 g : 500 ml) and subsequently by dispersion of the float samples from first step in acetone (cenosphere : acetone ratio 50 g : 500 ml) (Fig. 1). The mixture was shaken for ten minutes and allowed to settle for 2 h. The ‘float’ and ‘settled’ cenospheres were separated and dried. The logic behind selection of fraction A for flotation was that this particular fraction had

Fig. 1. (a) Flotation of cenospheres belonging to fraction A in water. (b) Dispersion of the floated samples in acetone.

the minimum amount of broken cenospheres.

Results and discussion

As mentioned earlier, the basic objective of the present work was to devise suitable methodologies to segregate the broken cenospheres from the intact shell one as far as possible – the latter having higher position in the utility scale. Further, another aim was to obtain a fraction of light “intact shell cenospheres” for specific need oriented uses. Such attempts require extensive characterisation of cenospheres at the various stages of isolation/separation. Results of such analysis, reported in the following sections point towards successful development of methodologies for the separation/isolation of cenospheres.

Physico-chemical properties of as received and beneficiated cenospheres :

The representative samples (see materials and methods) of as received cenospheres were characterised as far as their physical, chemical and mineralogical properties are concerned. The mean bulk and apparent densities of the as received cenospheres are 540 and 711 kg m⁻³ respectively (Table 1). The bulk and apparent densities of the size classified cenosphere fractions A, B, C, D and E (see materials and methods) are generally less than the as received ones, except for fraction E which is quite high. The higher density of cenospheres belonging to fraction E is possibly due to the very high content of broken

cenospheres. Higher content of intact shell cenospheres obviously will lead to lighter cenosphere particles owing to entrapment of air/gases in the hollow space. Support for this proposition is reflected in the observation – the low density cenospheres belonging to fractions A, B, C and D have higher “intact shell cenosphere” content.

Mineralogical analysis (XRD) indicates the presence of mullite and quartz as the principal phases, with hematite and magnetite as the Fe-bearing phases (Fig. 2). The chemical composition does not show any significant deviation from those of low carbon fly ash generated in super thermal power plants in Eastern India (Table 2)¹⁶.

Fig. 2. XRD of as received cenospheres.

Weight percentage of the various size classified fractions of cenospheres :

Size classification of as received cenospheres, using sieves (see materials and methods) resulted in different size classified fractions of cenospheres (A-E). Nearly, 90–96% (by weight) of cenospheres with arithmetic mean diameter (AMD) 179.32 μm, was obtained (fraction A). Contributions to the total mass of as received cenospheres by other size classified fractions are marginal (0.2–5%) (Table 3). Size classification of the as received cenospheres by ‘wet sieving’ with sieves of identical mesh sizes yielded results that are not too far away from that obtained by dry

Table 1. Bulk and apparent density of cenospheres

Entry	Sample detail	Bulk density (kg m ⁻³) ^a	Apparent density (kg m ⁻³) ^a
1.	As received	540	711
2.	Fraction A	450	682
3.	Fraction B	400	670
4.	Fraction C	370	643
5.	Fraction D	260	533
6.	Fraction E	690	825
7.	Float	400	618
8.	Settle	490	814

^aResults reported are average of twenty experimental results.

Table 2. Chemical composition (% by weight) of cenospheres (as received)

Na ₂ O	0.093	SiO ₂	58.3	CaO	0.58	MnO	0.63	Cu	0.002	Rb	0.005	Nb	0.001
MgO	0.68	SO ₃	0.26	TiO ₂	1.32	Fe ₂ O ₃	1.29	Yb	0.003	Zr	0.013	–	–
Al ₂ O ₃	34.3	K ₂ O	0.71	Cr ₂ O ₃	0.13	Ni	0.06	Ba	0.572	Sr	0.015	–	–

Table 3. Weight percentage distribution of cenospheres belonging to fraction A-E

Entry	A	B	C	D	E
1.	90.8(91.21) ^a	1(0.81)	4.1(3.92)	0.3(0.24)	1.1(0.88)
2.	90.5(90.8)	1.1(1.01)	4.2(3.8)	0.1(0.4)	1(0.92)
3.	93.7(90.9)	0.8(1.2)	3(4)	0.6(0.8)	1.1(1.08)
4.	93.7(94.5)	0.5(0.43)	2.8(2.58)	0.7(0.87)	1.1(0.8)
5.	87.7(92.1)	4(0.6)	4.5(3.4)	0.2(0.1)	0.8(0.15)
6.	91.1(94.7)	2(1.03)	4.1(3.6)	0.1(0.14)	0.9(0.8)
7.	90.1(91.7)	1.2(1.8)	3.4(3.21)	0.2(0.15)	1.1(0.3)
8.	96.5(92.6)	0.8(0.67)	1.1(0.92)	0.2(0.15)	0.7(0.4)
9.	91.7(95.6)	1.4(0.98)	1.9(1.51)	0.4(1.4)	0.5(1.1)
10.	93(94.3)	1.1(1)	1.6(1.5)	0.6(1.6)	0.7(0.6)

^aValues in parentheses refer to the data for wet sieving.

sieving, thus suggesting that comminution is at best a minor proposition. It appears that ‘sheer hardness’ associated with cenosphere particles prevents much comminution.

Particle size distribution of as received and various size classified cenospheres :

Particle size analysis using laser based particle size analyzer was carried out for as received and different size classified fractions. D_{10} , D_{50} , D_{90} and AMDs are presented in Table 4. As received cenospheres have moderately high values. On the other hand cenosphere particles belonging to the size classified fraction A has substantially high values for the similar parameters. As expected, there is a dipping trend in the values for these parameters for the size classified fractions B-D. Notable results are obtained for the floated cenosphere fractions (in acetone). As fraction E contains mainly the broken irregular shaped cenospheres so it was discarded in this regard. Perusal of entry 7 of Table 4 reveals that D_{10} ,

D_{50} , D_{90} and span values for the floated cenospheres are comparatively much lower than the similar entries for cenospheres belonging to the fraction A. There is almost a reduction of 14–15% in these values. Hence the floated cenospheres are likely to provide more compactness to the finished product when used as fillers.

The grain size distributions of the as received, size classified fractions A-D, floated and settled cenospheres are presented in Fig. 3. Mostly these are asymmetric distributions. The extent of asymmetry in an asymmetric distribution is measured by skewness. A perusal of grain size distributions for the acetone float and settled cenospheres reveals that these are right handed skewed, signifying that all these fractions have relatively lesser amounts of particles with higher particle size. The smaller particle size range, lower density, uniform distribution of particle size coupled with high abundance of intact shell cenospheres makes the floated cenospheres quite useful for industrial application.

Morphological analysis of cenospheres :

Morphological analysis (using SEM) of as received cenospheres and its size classified fractions (A-E) is given in Fig. 4. It was found that the as received sample contain both intact shell and broken cenospheres. On the other hand size classified fraction A, is enriched in intact shell cenospheres. The amount of intact shell cenospheres progressively decreased from size classified fractions (B-E).

The SEM image of the float and settled cenospheres obtained by floating the cenospheres in acetone belonging to the size classified fraction A are shown in Fig. 5. A thorough perusal reveals that the float one contains mostly intact shell cenospheres whereas the broken

Table 4. Particle size distribution of as received, size classified (A-D), floated and settled cenospheres

Entry	Sample	D_{10}	D_{50}	D_{90}	Span	AMD
1.	As received	103.29	163.8	297.6	1.18	181.65
2.	Fraction A	91.95	156.25	307.02	1.37	179.32
3.	Fraction B	78.54	101.48	171.96	0.92	117.75
4.	Fraction C	60.68	84.57	139.50	0.83	95.87
5.	Fraction D	16.29	37.12	73.53	1.54	41.23
6.	Float	79.54	134.45	249.40	1.26	15.26
7.	Settled	113.60	178.78	310.14	1.10	179.14

D_{10} = 10% of the particles < this diameter, D_{50} = 50% of the particles < this diameter, D_{90} = 90% of the particle < this diameter, AMD = arithmetic mean diameter. The values reported are in μm , except span which is a ratio and equals to $(D_{90} - D_{10})/D_{50}$.

Fig. 3. Particle size distribution profile of (a) as received, (b) fraction A, (c) fraction B, (d) fraction C, (e) fraction D, (f) acetone float, (g) acetone settled cenospheres.

Fig. 4. SEM image of (a) as received, (b) fraction A, (c) fraction B, (d) fraction C, (e) fraction D, (f) fraction E.

Fig. 5. SEM image of (a) acetone float, (b) acetone settled, (c) broken porous wall cenospheres.

cenospheres are segregated in the settled one. Another interesting observation was that the shell walls of cenospheres are porous. It implies that not only the hollowness of the intact shell cenospheres, but also the fine closed pores within the shell wall contribute to thermal and sound insulating property of cenospheres.

High Resolution Transmission Electron Microscopy

(HRTEM) of as received cenospheres reveals that the cenosphere particle may be spherical but surface is uneven (Fig. 6). Some aluminosilicate particles remain fused on the surface. ‘Pothole’ like structures may be present on the surfaces of cenospheres. The depths of such pot holes vary (0.1–0.25 μm). Fissures also appear. However, the pot hole in this particular case does not pen-

Dey *et al.* : A simple cost effective method for obtaining intact shell cenospheres from as received one

Fig. 6. HRTEM image of acetone float cenospheres : (a) general overview, (b) fused aluminosilicate particles, (c) pothole and fissure on cenosphere surface.

erate the shell wall, suggesting that the pores on the surface of cenospheres may not be always penetrating deep but are often topical in nature.

Conclusion

As received cenospheres collected from ash lagoon of Rihand Super Thermal Power Plant are widely variant in nature as far as their particle sizes are concerned. A rigorous morphological analysis reveals that both broken and 'intact shell' cenospheres are present. The bulk and apparent densities are in the normal range as found in literature. The chemical composition is similar to some of the low carbon Indian fly ash.

Size classification using sieves of mesh size 150, 250, 300 and 400 yields several fractions, out of which the coarsest fraction is highly enriched in intact shell cenospheres. The total weight percentage of this fraction is also quite high. Intact shell cenosphere enrichment along with higher weight percentage makes this particular fraction quite useful for industry as compared to the as received cenospheres. Another fraction obtained by flotation of cenospheres in acetone belonging to fraction A, appear to be more homogenous as far as the presence of intact shell cenosphere is concerned. The particle size of the cenospheres is also less as compared to the as received cenospheres. The lower densities of this particular fraction also add to its preferential use as fillers.

References

1. S. Torey, "Coal Ash Utilization : Fly Ash, Bottom Ash and Slag", Noyes Data Corp., Park Ridge, NJ, USA, 1978.
2. E. Raask, *J. Inst. Fuel*, 1968, **41**, 334.
3. M. Shpirt, V. Kler and I. Pertsikov, "Inorganic Components of Coals", Moscow, Chimia, 240 [in Russian], 1990.
4. E. V. Sokol, N. V. Maksimova, N. I. Volkova, E. N. Nigmatulina and A. E. Frenkel, *Fuel Process Technol.*, 2000, **67**, 35.
5. S. V. Vassilev and C. G. Vassileva, *Fuel Process Technol.*, 1996, **47**, 261.
6. R. J. Lauf, *Fuel*, 1981, **60**, 1177.
7. E. Raask, *J. Eng. Power*, 1966, **88**, 40.
8. R. Kruger and P. In. Toit-du, The 9th International Ash Use Symposium, EPRI. GS-7162. 1991, **3**, 76-1-76-20.
9. S. Ghosal and S. A. Self, *Fuel*, 1995, **74**, 522.
10. S. Vassilev, R. Menendez, M. Diaz-Somoano and M. Rosa Martinez-Tarazona, *Fuel*, 2004, **83**, 585.
11. N. Voina and D. Todor, "Analytical methods for coal and coal products", ed. C. In Karr, Academic Press, New York, USA, 1978.
12. <http://www.primaryinfo.com/projects/cenospheres.htm> (May 21, 2013).
13. L. Ya, A. L. Kizilshtein, Shpitsgluz and V. G. Rylov, *Khim. Tverd. Topl.*, 1987, **6**, 122.
14. R. Kruger, *Fuel*, 1997, **76**, 777.
15. S. P. McBride, A. Shukla and A. Bose, *J. Mat. Sci.*, 2002, **37**, 4217.
16. A. Sarkar, R. Rano, G. Udaybhanu and A. K. Basu, *Fuel Proc. Technol.*, 2006, **87**, 259.

